

AVAILABILITY AND UTILISATION OF EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS IN PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOL IN OREDO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF EDO STATE

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Abstract

This study was carried out to ascertain availability and utilisation of educational materials and effective administration of private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. Three research questions were raised and answered to achieve the purpose of the study. The study employed descriptive survey research method. The population of the study was 2,728 students from 30 private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government of Edo State, while 22% total of 600 students, made up the sample for the study. This was done using the simple random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection were a validated checklist from the Ministry of Education and a self-constructed questionnaire. Data were analysed using frequency count, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation. Findings of the study revealed that the available educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State are radios, tape recorders, and accessories, bulletin board, flannel board, flash cards, flash cards, motion pictures, film strips, slides, biology laboratories computer instructors, chemistry laboratory technologist, physics laboratory technologist, biology laboratory technologists, agriculture laboratory technologists, workshop technician, music instructors and the major problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State are lack of electricity, inadequate tools, poor condition of equipment, lack of pipe borne water, lack of storage facility and irregular maintenance. In view of the findings and conclusions from the study, it was recommended that school management should conduct regular checks to ensure that available educational resources are regularly and properly and that the State Ministry of Education should as much as possible, visit schools in order to have a first-hand information of challenges facing the schools so as to determine the best possible solutions to those problems.

Keywords: Availability, Educational Materials, Private Secondary School Utilisation,

Introduction

Education is universally recognised as an instrument for social, political, scientific and technological development. This is the reason why no society can afford to toy with the education of its citizens, as this could result in a snail speed development. According to Afework (2024), education is an aggregate of all the processes by which a child or young adult develops his/her abilities, attitudes and other forms of behaviour which are of value to the society in which they live. It is a conscious training of the young generation for a life which would be useful to them and to the society to which they belong.

This presupposes that there is a symbiotic relationship between the quality of education offered in any country and the level of development in such a nation. This is because, just as quality education determines national development, the level of development or advancement of any nation also determines the quality of education that can be provided (Aganze, 2018). This is the reason for a growing concern about the quality of education that is offered in schools all over the country. However, this presumed quality of education cannot be achieved without adequate educational materials and proper utilisation of the same.

Educational materials encompass a range of items used for teaching and learning purposes. They are also seen as a collection of tools and equipment that can be used effectively for classroom communication and in the management and administration of education. In the view of Agwubike and Ogbouma (2020), educational materials are all equipment within the educational system which are directed towards the achievement of general educational objectives, which is the total development of the individual. This implies that educational

materials include both instructional materials and other educational

facilities like offices, libraries, laboratories, health centres, among others.

The importance of educational materials in bringing about an all-around educated individual cannot be overemphasised. This is because these materials are sine qua non for effective behavioural change in learners. This explains why Eze and Aja (2024) stressed that educational materials promote efficiency of education by improving the quality of teaching and learning. It offers a variety of learning experiences, individually or in combination, to meet different teaching and learning experiences.

A discussion of educational materials will naturally focus on the availability and utilisation of these materials. This is particularly true as their availability and utilisation will contribute to effective administration of the educational system, while crowded classrooms, non-availability of competent teachers, as well as non-availability and or poor utilisation of instructional materials will not only frustrate management efforts, but can contribute to poor performance of students.

Availability of educational materials refers to the extent to which educational materials are physically present at the point of need in their correct specification and number. In other words, availability of education resources indicates that the needed materials are within reach at the proper time in the right quality and quantity. This presupposes that even when the materials or resources can be seen but are not accessible, they are considered unavailable. In addition, educational materials are also not available until they have the right quality and quantity (Agwubike & Ogbouma, 2020). This is because the central aim of providing the materials is to enable the achievement of educational objectives in all of its ramifications and so poor quality or inadequate materials are considered anathema to the goal.

Educational materials are expected to be adequately and qualitatively provided to create favourable environment for administration as well as the teaching-learning process in secondary schools in order to enhance the level of output. For instance, Asabiaka (2018) indicated that a standard teacher-student ratio in Nigerian secondary schools is 1:40. Similarly, a standard chemistry laboratory is meant to serve only 30 students at a time and would be considered inadequate when utilized by more than that number of students. It is, however, not uncommon that educational materials like libraries, workshops, audio-visuals in most secondary schools are either non-existent, or dilapidated. The availability of most of these facilities however, will only be meaningful if they are well utilised.

Utilization of educational materials is the extent of usage of school buildings, laboratories, library, workshops, chairs, desks, chalkboard, computers, audio-visuals and other educational materials for the attainment of educational objectives. It is the appropriateness of the usage of available educational materials during the teaching and learning process. In other words, it is one thing to use educational materials; it is another thing to use them properly. This probably explains why Al-Sharari (2018) opined that educational supervisors should pay more attention to ensure the correct usage of instructional materials so that the benefit of using them can be maximised. This implies that their proper utilisation influences lesson clarity, student engagement, curriculum coverage, and ultimately learning outcomes. However, across educators and learners face persistent and interrelated problems that hinder the effective use of these materials.

Some of the problems include the availability of educational resources, infrastructure, teacher competence, relevance, maintenance, policy, and user behaviour. They all interact to produce persistent under-utilisation of educational materials. Addressing utilisation, therefore, requires multi-level interventions, from national financing and procurement reforms to school-level capacity building, infrastructure investment, context-sensitive material development, and

continuous teacher professional development, so that materials move

from mere presence to pedagogically effective use.

The availability of educational materials as well as their utilisation are very pertinent issues in any educational programme. In recent times, it has been observed that most private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State lack the required level of educational resources. This is being considered as one of the reasons for the poor academic performance of students, both at internal and external examinations. This situation may likely persist if efforts are not made to improve the condition of resources in terms of their availability, especially instructional materials or if those available are not adequately utilised. This hinged on the report of Asabiaka (2018), that the level of success of most educational programmes is greatly dependent on the degree of availability and utilisation of up-to-date facilities, equipment and supplies. This is because they form the hub around which such programmes revolve.

Since secondary education occupies a very key position in the educational development of individuals, hence the need for adequate care to be taken to ensure that necessary materials are available to help achieve the educational objectives at this level. It is against this background that this study examined the availability and utilisation of educational materials in private secondary Oredo Local Government Area of schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, increasing attention has been paid to the educational performance of students in Nigeria, particularly in urban centres like Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The availability and utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools become critical mediating factors. These materials, including textbooks, instructional aids, laboratory equipment, ICT tools, and visual learning resources, are essential for improving learning

experiences, enhancing student confidence, and mitigating the adverse effects of poor home environments on academic performance.

The consequences of inadequate availability and poor utilisation of educational materials are far-reaching. For students, it leads to low academic achievement, reduced interest in school activities, and diminished self-esteem, especially when compared with peers in better-equipped schools. On a broader level, these deficiencies tend to compromise the development of human capital, leading to a generation of youths who may be ill-prepared for higher education or the job market. Families are burdened with the financial and emotional costs of seeking alternative educational solutions, while society suffers from increased dropout rates and underemployment among youths who might otherwise have thrived in a supportive learning environment.

Given the above concerns, there is a compelling need to assess the actual state of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area. It is crucial to determine whether these resources are not only available but also effectively utilised by teachers and students to support learning. By identifying specific gaps, the study could inform policy actions, guide school improvement strategies, and support the development of interventions aimed at improving student learning outcomes.. The problem of this study, therefore, is to examine the availability and utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. What are the available educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State?

2. What is the level of utilization of educational materials in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State?
3. What are the problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State?

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine the availability and utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. Specifically, this study seeks to

1. explore the availability of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
2. determine the level of utilization of educational materials in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
3. investigate the the problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Methodology

Design of the Study

This study employed the descriptive survey research method. This approach was considered appropriate because it enabled the researcher to collect information from a representative sample on the issue of the availability, utilisation and problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of a total of two thousand, seven hundred and twenty-eight (2,728) students from thirty (30) private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government of Edo State.

Sampling and Sampling Techniques

A total of six hundred (600) students from thirty (30) private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government of Edo State constituted the sample for the study. A breakdown shows that 20 students were selected from each school using the simple random sampling technique. This is to ensure fairness and eliminate bias.

Instrument for Data Collection

The data for this study were obtained using a validated checklist from the Edo Ministry and Education and a self-constructed questionnaire titled “Availability and Utilisation of Educational Materials (AUEM)” The questionnaire will be in two sections; A and B. The section A provided information on demographic variables of the respondents such as age, sex, class etc. while section B contained 50 items which were meant to provide answers to the issues raised in the research questions raised. Responses were rated using a three-point scale of Not Available, Moderately Available, Highly Available, for availability, Never utilised, Occasionally Utilised, Always Utilised, for level of utilisation and a four-point modified Likert scale of Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree, problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials.

Validity of the Instrument

The research instruments were examined for face and content validity. In this regard, draft copies of the questionnaire and checklist were given to the three experts in the Faculty of

Education, University of Benin, Benin City, for scrutiny. Their

suggestions were taken into consideration in producing the final copy of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

To determine the reliability of the instrument, the internal consistency reliability method was adopted. To achieve this, the instrument was pre-tested on 20 participants from the population, but not part of the sample of the study. The data collected were analysed using Cronbach's alpha statistics to determine the stability of the instrument. This process yielded a reliability index of 0.81, 0.64, and 0.66 for sections 1, 2, and 3, respectively. This resulted in an average of 0.70, indicating that the instrument is very reliable.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for the study were analysed using descriptive statistics comprising of frequency count, simple percentage, mean and standard deviation. The criterion mean for decision-making for the research questions was 2.50. Items with a mean of 2.50 were in agreement with the item statement, while those with a mean value below 2.50 implied disagreement with the item statement.

Results

Research Question One: What are the available educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Response Ratings of the Available Educational Materials in Private Secondary Schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

S/N	Educational Materials	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Radio	1.13	.527	N A
2.	Public Address System	1.87	.527	M A
3.	Tape Recorder and Accessories	1.05	.710	N A
4.	Chalk board	1.99	.561	M A

5.	Chalks	1.99	.557	M A
6.	Bulletin board	2.00	.674	H A
7.	Flannel Board	1.21	.667	N A
8.	Flash Cards	2.34	.767	H A
9.	Poster	2.28	.953	H A
10.	Pictures	2.36	.866	H A
11.	Models	1.92	.816	M A
12.	Charts	2.37	.799	H A
13.	Motion Pictures	1.68	.829	M A
14.	Film Strips	1.89	.895	M A
15.	Slides	2.02	.896	H A
16.	Computer set	2.32	.664	H A
17.	Television Set	2.33	.575	H A
18.	Sound strip projector	1.43	.741	N A
19.	Library	2.31	.645	H A
20.	Counselling Room	1.61	.662	M A
21.	Computer Room	1.65	.704	M A
22.	Chemistry Laboratory	1.81	.743	M A
23.	Physics Laboratory	1.92	.775	M A
24.	Biology Laboratory	1.68	.830	M A
25.	Agriculture Laboratory	1.95	.876	M A
26.	Home Economics Kitchen	1.81	.902	M A
27.	Introductory Technology Workshop	1.21	.923	N A
28.	Music theatre	1.23	.858	N A
29.	Health centre	1.81	.865	M A
30.	Liberian	2.40	.672	H A
31.	Guidance Counsellor	1.32	.739	N A
32.	Computer Instructor	2.00	.820	H A
33.	Chemistry Laboratory Technologist	1.28	.785	N A
34.	Physics Laboratory Technologist	1.15	.864	N A
35.	Biology Laboratory Technologist	1.36	.872	N A
36.	Agriculture Laboratory Technologist	1.32	.844	N A

37.	Home Economics Kitchen Attendants	1.36	.838	M A
38.	Workshop Technician	1.03	.849	N A
39.	Music Instructor	1.21	.863	N A
40.	Health Officer	1.63	.854	M A

Mean Benchmark: 1.00 – 1.50 N A, 1.51 – 1.99 M A, 2.00 – 2.50 H A

Key: N.A- Not Available, M.A- Moderately Available, H.A- Highly Available

On the availability of education resources, data in Table 1 shows that eight (08) of the educational materials that is, items 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 15, 16, 17, 19, 30 and 32 with standard deviation of 0.67, 0.78, 0.95, 0.87, 0.80, 0.90, 0.66, 0.56, 0.65, 0.67, and 0.82 respectively, were identified as highly available. Similarly, twenty-four (24) of them that is, items 2, 4, 5, 11, 13, 14, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 37 and 40 with standard deviation of 0.53, 0.56, 0.56, 0.82, 0.83, 0.90, 0.66, 0.70, 0.74, 0.78, 0.83, 0.88, 0.90, 0.84 and 0.85, respectively, were identified as moderately available, while another eight (08) of the educational resources, that is, items 1, 3, 7, 18, 27, 28, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 38 and 39, with standard deviation of 0.53, 0.71, 0.68, 0.74, 0.92, 0.86, 0.74, 0.79, 0.86, 0.87, 0.84, 0.85 and 0.86, respectively, were considered not available. This means that the available educational materials in secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State are bulletin boards, flash cards, poster, pictures, charts, slides, computer sets, television sets, libraries, librarians and computer instructors.

Research Question 2: What is the level of utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Response Ratings of the Level of Utilisation of Educational Materials in Private Secondary Schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

S/N	Educational Materials	Mean	SD	Remarks
1.	Radio	1.26	.493	N U
2.	Public Address System	1.58	.558	O U
3.	Tape Recorder and Accessories	1.35	.694	N U
4.	Chalk board	1.62	.717	O U

5.	Chalks	1.78	.298	O U
6.	Bulletin board	2.00	.783	A U
7.	Flannel Board	1.38	.659	N U
8.	Flash Cards	1.69	.716	O U
9.	Poster	1.87	.885	O U
10.	Pictures	2.29	.788	A U
11.	Models	1.23	.895	N U
12.	Charts	2.47	.824	A U
13.	Motion Pictures	1.71	.813	O U
14.	Film Strips	1.53	.829	O U
15.	Slides	2.32	.874	A U
16.	Computer set	2.46	.645	A U
17.	Television Set	2.37	.584	A U
18.	Sound strip projector	1.31	.780	N U
19.	Library	1.61	.438	O U
20.	Counselling Room	1.68	.671	O U
21.	Computer Room	2.00	.666	A U
22.	Chemistry Laboratory	1.63	.896	O U
23.	Physics Laboratory	1.55	.905	O U
24.	Biology Laboratory	1.65	.866	O U
25.	Agriculture Laboratory	1.71	.885	O U
26.	Home Economics Kitchen	1.88	.900	O U
27.	Introductory Technology Workshop	1.10	.918	N U
28.	Music theatre	1.23	.896	N U
29.	Health centre	1.87	.671	O U
30.	Liberian	2.10	.707	O U
31.	Guidance Counsellor	1.22	.828	N U
32.	Computer Instructor	2.23	.779	A U
33.	Chemistry Laboratory Technologist	1.19	.762	N U
34.	Physics Laboratory Technologist	1.21	.370	N U
35.	Biology Laboratory Technologist	1.21	.867	N U
36.	Agriculture Laboratory Technologist	1.30	.895	N U

37.	Home Economics Kitchen Attendants	2.19	.785	O U
38.	Workshop Technician	1.18	.787	N U
39.	Music Instructor	1.32	.907	N U
40.	Health Officer	1.71	.805	O U

Mean Benchmark: 1.00 – 1.50 Never Utilised, 1.51 – 1.99 Occasionally Utilised, 2.00 – 2.50 Always Utilised

Key: N. U- Never utilised, O- Occasionally utilised, A. U.- Always utilised

On the issue of utilisation, data in Table 2 shows that eight (08) of the educational resources, that is, items 6, 10, 12, 15, 16, 17, 21, and 32, with standard deviation of 0.78, 0.79, 0.82, 0.87, 0.65, 0.58, 0.67, 0.78 respectively, were always utilised. In the same vein, eighteen (18) of them, that is, items 2, 4, 5, 8, 9, 13, 14, 19, 20, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 29, 30, 37 and 40, with standard deviation of 0.56, 0.72, 0.30, 0.72, 0.89, 0.81, 0.83, 0.44, 0.67, 0.90, 0.91, 0.87, 0.89, 0.90, 0.67, 0.71, 0.76 and 0.81, respectively, were occasionally utilised, while fourteen (14) of them, that is, items 1, 3, 7, 11, 18, 27, 31, 33, 34, 35, 36, 38, and 39, with standard deviation of 0.49, 0.69, 0.66, 0.90, 0.78, 0.92, 0.90, 0.83, 0.76, 0.37, 0.87, 0.90, 0.79 and 0.91 respectively, were never utilised. This means that educational materials that are utilised in private secondary schools are bulletin board, pictures, charts, slides, computer set, television set, computer room and computer instructor.

Research Question Three: What are the problems encountered during the utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Table 3: Frequency Count and Percentage Responses Rating on the Problems Encountered During Utilisation of Educational Materials in Private Secondary Schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

S/N	Items	Yes	Percentage	No	Percentage	Comment
1.	Lack of Electricity	51	82.3	11	17.7	Encountered
2.	Inadequate tools	45	72.6	17	27.4	Encountered
3.	Poor condition of equipment	34	54.8	28	45.2	Encountered
4.	Lack of pipe-borne water	36	58.1	26	41.9	Encountered

5.	Insufficient time	6	9.7	56	90.3	Not Encountered
6.	Inadequate personnel	20	32.3	42	67.7	Not Encountered
7.	Lack of storage facility	33	53.2	29	46.8	Encountered
8.	Poor classroom spaces	15	24.2	47	75.8	Not Encountered
9.	Poor pedagogical skills	30	48.4	32	51.6	Not Encountered
10.	Irregular maintenance	34	54.8	28	45.2	Encountered

Data in Table 3 shows the problems encountered during the utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The responses of the participants of the study revealed that 51 of the respondents indicated that lack of electricity was a problem while 11 of them disagreed. Forty-five (45) of the participants agreed that inadequate tool was a problem while 17 of them disagreed. Thirty-four (34) of the respondents indicated that poor condition of equipment was a problem while 28 disagreed. Thirty-six (36) of the respondents opined that lack of pipe borne water was a problem while twenty-six (26) of them were negative on the issue. Similarly, six (6) of the respondents stated that insufficient time was a problem while fifty-six (56) of them disagreed, twenty (20) of the study participants stated that inadequate personnel constituted a problem while forty-two (42) of them disagreed. Still on the issue, thirty-three (33) of the study participants indicated that lack of storage facility constituted a problem to which twenty-nine (29) of them disagreed. For fifteen (15) of the respondents, poor classroom space was a problem while it was not for forty-seven (47) of them. In the same vein, thirty (30) of the respondents indicated that poor pedagogical skill was a problem while thirty-two (32) of them were negative on the issue. Thirty-four (34) of the study participants stated that irregular maintenance constituted a problem while twenty-eight (28) of

them disagreed on the issue. This means that lack of electricity, inadequate tools, poor condition of equipment, lack of pipe borne water, lack of storage facility and irregular maintenance are the major problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Discussion of Findings

The first finding emanating from research question revealed that the available educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State are bulletin boards, flash cards, poster, pictures, charts, slides, computer sets, television sets, libraries, librarians and computer instructors. This finding falls in line with classification of educational resources by NOUN into, Human Resources, Physical Materials, Financial Resources, Time Resources, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Resources, Community Resources and Instructional Media. Ikoya (2018) also grouped instructional media into three namely, Visuals, Audios and Audio-visuals. This classification accommodates the specific materials used to enhance the teaching learning process in particular and school administration in general.

Secondly, findings from the study revealed that educational materials that are utilised in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State include bulletin board, pictures, charts, slides, computer set, television set, computer room and computer instructor. This finding is supported by Akinfolarin, Ajayi and Oloruntegbe (2022), who appraised resource utilisation in Vocational and Technical Education in Selected Secondary schools in Southwest Nigeria and found that most of the required resources in Vocational and Technical Education were available, adequate and well utilised. However, it can be observed that educational resources under the purview of information and communication technology (ICT) were not utilised. This also corroborates the findings of Eze and Aja (2024) in their study on

the availability and utilization of information and communication

technology (ICT) in Ebonyi Local Government area of Ebonyi state which indicated that ICT devices are not adequately utilized, personnel to operate ICT devices are not adequately trained and most of the ICT devices are not in good working condition in schools studied.

Finally, finding from this study revealed that the major problems encountered during utilisation of educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State are; lack of electricity, inadequate tools, poor condition of equipment, lack of pipe borne water, lack of storage facility and irregular maintenance. In support of this finding, Ugwuanyi (2024) reported that most of the Nigerian primary schools are dilapidated due to inadequate funding while most tertiary institutions are living in their past glories. Such situation hinders effective teaching and learning, making the process rigorous and uninteresting to students and teachers. In the same vein, Owuamanam (2022) noted that the inadequacy of infrastructural facilities and lack of maintenance for available facilities were major problems facing the Nigerian educational system.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the available educational materials in private secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State include radio, tape recorder and accessories, bulletin board, flannel board, flash cards, flash cards, motion pictures, film strips, slides, biology laboratory, computer instructor, chemistry laboratory technologist, physics laboratory technologist, biology laboratory technologist, agriculture laboratory technologist, workshop technician and music instructor, only few were actively utilised. The issue of poor utilisation is attributed to the problems in schools such as lack of electricity, inadequate tools, poor condition of equipment, lack of pipe-borne water, lack of storage facility and irregular maintenance. Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations are offered

1. Efforts should be made by private school managers to ensure the availability of other necessary learning resources in the school environment
2. School management should conduct regular checks to ensure that available educational resources are regularly and properly utilised. They should also provide solutions to any problem preventing the utilisation of any educational resource
3. The Edo State Ministry of Education should visit schools as much as possible to gather first-hand information on challenges facing the schools to determine the best possible solutions to those problems.

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